

“5 G” INTERNET AND POPULATION OPINION ANALYSIS

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Abstract. This article presents the analysis of the answers to the questionnaire reflecting the personal opinion, knowledge and work of the population about the 5G Internet and the impact of its support on people and nature. The research was carried out in the form of a questionnaire, for five days, using the "Telegram" messenger. According to the results of the survey, 236 people read the questionnaires, but more than 113 people (48 %) actively answered the questions. 52% (123 people) read the questions but did not want to answer.

Key words: EMF (Electromagnet Field), 5 G Internet, human organism, human health, negative effect, harmfulness for nature, harmfulness for animals and plants, future technology.

1. Introduction

Humanity has entered the age of wireless technology, and this shows that much is known and unknown about its consequences. In accordance with the requirements of the times, humanity began to use these technologies more and more intensively. Scientists are conducting many studies to determine whether the 5G Internet has a negative effect on the human body and nature (plant and animal world). Some scientists say that the electromagnetic field is a factor that causes cancer, genetic diseases, memory loss [1, 2]. According to scientists' research, wireless technologies and EMF cause dangerous processes in the human body, in particular premature

aging, inflammation, damage to reproductive cells, damage to the brain, heart and even DNA molecules [3]. Installing 5G is like turning on a microwave oven and leaving the door open for life. 5 G waves are mutagenic and can change the molecular structures of living organisms. Among scientists, there are different and serious opinions about the negative effects of 5 G technologies, but the importance of conducting research on it is also increasing, which helps to draw clear conclusions about their use [4].

2. Method

The research was conducted in the form of a questionnaire. "Telegram" messenger was used for this purpose. The research was conducted anonymously for one week, consisting of 5 questions, two or three different answers, and 236 people got acquainted with the electronic questionnaire directly, of which 48% (113 people) answered the questions. 52% (123 people) of those who read the questionnaire did not answer the questionnaire questions.

Figure 1. Inactive (52 %) and active (48 %)

Questionnaire questions were made as follows: 1. Do you think 5 G (Internet) will have a negative effect on flora and fauna? 2. 5 G Internet is a guarantee of development; do you think it can have a negative effect on human health? 3. Do you believe that 5G Internet will be launched in our area in the near future? 4. It is no

secret that the 5 G Internet helps speed up development, but do you think that humanity will develop measures to protect itself from its negative effects in the future? 5. 5 Can 5 G Internet have a negative effect on the human psychology?

3. Results

Answers to survey questions were also put into diagrams and analyzed. "Do you think 5 G (Internet) will have a negative effect on flora and fauna?" 114 people answered the first question called, and the results were represented by the following diagram (Figure 2).

Figure 2.

The second question of the survey, that is, "5 G Internet is a guarantee of development; do you think it can have a negative effect on human health?" 111 people answered the question and the answers can be found in the diagram below (Figure 3).

Figure 3.

The third question of the survey, that is, "Do you believe that 5G Internet will be launched in our area in the near future?" 114 people answered the question and the results of the analysis are represented by diagram (Figure 4).

Figure 4.

The fourth question of the anonymous survey, that is, "It is no secret that the Internet helps speed up development, but do you think that humanity will develop measures to protect itself from its negative effects in the future?" 111 people answered the question, and these answers are represented by diagram (Figure 5).]

Figure 5.

The fifth question of the anonymous survey, "Can 5 G Internet have a negative effect on the human psychology?" 116 people answered the question, and the results are illustrated by diagram (Figure 6).

Figure 6.

4. Discussion

52% of those who took the questionnaire were inactive without answering the questions, and the share of those who were active was almost half of the participants (48%). According to the first question of the questionnaire, 35% of the respondents believed that 5G Internet has a negative effect on flora and fauna, another 35% said they did not know the fact and 30% said "there is no negative effect" and expressed their opinion. In the second question of the questionnaire, 63% of the respondents believed that 5G Internet has a negative effect on human health, 22% of people do not have any opinion on this, and 15% of people said that "it does not have a negative effect". In recent years, the percentage of respondents who do not believe that 5G Internet will be installed in our country has become the largest (45%). It turned out that 31% of the respondents believe in this, and 24% have no opinion. The largest share (46%) of respondents who believe that humanity will develop measures to protect itself (health) from the negative effects of 5 G Internet technologies in the future, 30% of respondents do not believe this, and 24% of people do not know. 64% of the respondents who believe that boarding school can have a negative effect on

the human psyche, 15% who believe that "it does not have a negative effect", and 21% who do not have a firm opinion about it.

5. Conclusion

It is difficult to make clear judgments and draw conclusions because the respondents' answers express different and contradictory opinions. However, the existence of unbiased opinions about 5G Internet in the population will help to draw clear conclusions in further research.

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